

Effects of High Performance Work Practices (Hpwp's) and Teacher's Morale in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

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Received: June 10, 2025; Accepted: August 31, 2025; Published: September 8, 2025.

Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17081194>

Abstract: The study investigated the relationship between high performance work practices (HPWP'S) and teacher's morale in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. A cluster sample of 123 teachers in the public senior secondary school in Rivers state responded. For the data analysis and hypothesis testing; descriptive statistics and pearson product moment with the aid of SPSS 2.0 were used respectively. Two main high-performance work practices were identified by the analysis; compensation and benefits then promotion. These two practices have positive significant relationship with teacher's morale in the public senior secondary school in Rivers State. These study thereby enlightens the management of Rivers state senior secondary school board to effectively implement these practices that could boost teachers morale and their quality of life in order to achieve the educational goals of the organization.

Keywords: High performance work practices (HPWP'S), compensation and benefit, promotion, teacher's morale.

Introduction

Teachers are pivot on which educational system revolve. They are drivers to student's excellent academic performance. If the morale of the teacher is high the achievement of the students would be high Lumiden (2001). Morale refers to the degree to which a worker feels inspired, motivated or stimulated to become self-driven towards contributing optimally to the achievement of

organizational goals. It is a psychological construct which reveals how workers perceive the reward they receive in relation to the ideographic need disposition and compare the same with their colleagues (Weihrich & Koontz, 2010). Morale is different quality that can be described in many ways Hendri (2010) describes Morales as the spirit or work which is essentially a manifestation of high morale.

The spirit or morale in work is the behaviour of a person that describes the work, excitement and sincerity in carrying out a job that arises pleasure, that causes a person better in completion of the work in achieving the goals already set by the company (Ramadhany et al (2013). Where teacher's morale is high students typically show high- achievement (Burke and Cooper, 2010). But when teacher morale disintegrates, achievement steepens and so many problems emerges. High morale usually leads to enthusiasm, punctuality. Creativity, innovativeness, seriousness and empathy in the behaviour of teaching staff in class and school activities. A high morale teacher is a happy, serious and active one. Who looks forward to another day in school? He or she is satisfied and proud of his profession and contributes immensely to organisation success. Flowing from the above relevance of teacher's morale, is where High performance work practice (HPWP'S) comes to play. HPWP'S is a bundle of specific human resource management practices (Long et al., 2012) that can affect employee behaviour in the workplace. These study will look at two dimensions of HPWPS such as compensation and benefit and promotion according to (Grobler, 2018) as predicting teachers morale. Many researchers have investigated HPWP'S and operation efficiency and competitiveness (Sarikwal and

Grupta, 2013), few research investigated the extent to which HPWP'S affected employee behaviour in terms of labour productivity, turnover employee absenteeism as well as the financial well-being of organizations (Aguta and Balcoghi, 2015; Armstrong and Taylor, 2017; Butter and MCEVoy, 2012; Guthrie et al., 2009; Hoque et al., 2017; Kehoe, 2013; Melesse, 2016; Messers et al., 2011; Molr & Zogh, 2008; Shun & Konrad, 2017; White and Bryson, 2013). Scarce information is found on the impact of HPWP'S on employee morale especially in the educational sector. Hence the purpose of this study, is to investigate the relationship between HPWP'S and teacher's morale in public senior secondary school in Rivers state, Nigeria.

Without reservation the degree to which public senior secondary school teachers, engage in moonlighting or engage in private ventures or petty trading even during official hours for extra income to argument official salaries (Amaewhule, 2006) is alarming. Trends in Nigeria have shown that teachers are the most owed workers by successive governments, particularly state government. It was based on this that Agburu (2012) argued that salaries should not only be adequate but also prompt and show some elements of equality. Salary movement of public senior secondary teacher has not be effectively managed The

teachers for about 15 years has not received an increment in their salary, even the minimum wage of Buhari administration (2018) was effectively implemented rather, unexplainable and frequent deductions of salaries is being experienced among Rivers state public senior secondary teachers, The salary doesn't come on time and it is inadequate. A lot of teachers are leaving in borrowings to take care of their family. Depression, sicknesses and premature death surfaces. All these have dampened the teaching staff morale. Compensation which deals with every types of reward, IvanCeivich (2006) creates good morale teachers. Once workers perceive that certain behaviour or performance would earn them a specified amount of financial reward, they become self-driven and motivated to get such prospective reward but when such is denied or delayed their morale become low.

Benefits which is opined by Armstrong et al. (2013) as part of additional remuneration system in the form of cash of various types, may be in the form of insurance services to employees, benefits of old age or some expenses incurred outside of work is not effectively managed in this sector of education in Rivers state. Retires do not get their pensions as at when due, gratuities are delayed, no medical benefit, even no leave benefits as when compared to other employees in some organization. This is

very demoralizing. Discouraging new recruits into the education sector Public senior secondary school teachers in River State, usually expect to receive promotion after three years has elapsed. This promotion implies that their salaries would be raised and they would attain the level where they would be qualified for the post of a vice- principal, Director and even a permanent secretary .Sadly, these teachers rarely get promotions as at when due. This sinks the teacher's morale and makes many of them to display negative altitude to work like absenteeism, truancy, quarrel, depression, tardiness, rebellion, non-challancy, dissatisfaction and their kinds. this study seeks to investigate the relationships between compensation and benefits of teachers morale in public senior secondary school in River state and examine the relationship between promotion and teachers moral in public senior secondary school in Rivers state

Methodology

Research design

The research design employed in this study is cross sectional survey which supports the use of questionnaire to collect data from participation for a short period of time (Sekera & Bougie, 2016). Target population for this study is public senior secondary

school operating within Port Harcourt metropolis which is 15 schools in number and 708 teachers currently (RSSSSB statistics 2021). On the other hand, the accessible population comprises of the public senior secondary school clustered within Garrison, Trans Amadi axis of Port Harcourt Rivers state. With this criterion in Place the accessible population is 203 public senior secondary school teacher. The Krejcie Morgan formula at (5%) level of confidence was used to derive the sample size of 134. 134 copies of questionnaires were distributed but 121 copies were correctly filled and used for data analysis. Validity was determined using face validity. Cronbach alpha test was used to ascertain the reliability of the instrument. Pearson product moment served as a statistical tool to test the formulated hypothesis with the aid of IBM SPSS 22.0

Operational Measures of Variables

The instrument was divided into three sections. Section 'A' contains the profiles of the participants section B has the 8 statements items for the independent variable which is high performance work practices, measured in terms of compensation and benefits and promotion. and adapted from the work of posthumous et al (2013:184) while section C contains 8 statement items on teachers morale which was adapted from the work of Azwar .S(2009: 30). Measurement Scales employed was five- point like scales ranging from 5- strongly agree to 1- neither agree nor disagree. Face validity was used to determine the validity of the instrument. Apart from the above Cronbach and reliability test was carried out to measure the consistency of the instrument used for data collection.

The Cronbach α results showed that Compensation and benefits has α coefficient of 0.74, promotion 0.78, and teacher morale 0.82

Results and Discussion

Table 1 Respondents Profiles

Description	Frequency	Percentages
Gender		
Male	28	22.8
Female	95	77.2
Age		
35 or less	20	16.3
36-45	53	43.1
Overs 45	50	40.6
Educational Background		
Bachelor Degree	81	65.9
Master Degree	34	27.6
PhD Degree	8	6.5
Length of Work Service		
1-10years	45	36.6
11-20	45	36.6
21 or over	33	28.8
Grade Level		
8-G10	62	50.4
G11-G13	53	43.1
G14-G16	8	6.6
Marital Status		
Single	10	8.1
Married	90	73.2
Separated/Divorced	6	4.9
Widow/Widower	17	13.8

Source Field Survey (2021)

Result of gender distribution showed that 95 respondents representing 77.2% are females while 28 respondents representing 22.8% are males. This implies that females are of great number in the teaching section as at the time the study was carried out. Age brackets results showed that 40.6% are within the age bracket of 46 years and above. 53 respondents representing 43.1% are within the age brackets of 36-45 years and 20

respondents representing 16.3% fall within 18-35 years. Educational background of the respondents revealed 81 participants representing 65.98% are bachelor degree holders, 34 participants representing 27.6% are holder of master degree and 8 participants representing 6.5% are holders of PH.D degree this implies teachers of public senior secondary schools are all graduates of Tertiary institutions. The

length of working service of the public senior secondary school teachers here varies from less than 10years to over 20years in services. Teachers in public senior secondary school are graded according to their years and experience in service,, respectively. Ranging from Grade level 08

to grade level 16 in their career ladder Just about 8 persons which is 0.6% of the teacher have reached the peak of in the career leader among the teaching staff, as at the time of study. Majority of the teachers that participated are married, very few are either single, separated or a widow/widower.

Table 2 Hypothesis One Result Correlation

		Compensation and benefits	Teachers morale
Compensation and benefits teachers morale	Pearson correlation	1	.830**
	Sig (2. Tailed)		.000
	N	123	123
	Person correlation significant (2 tailed)	.830**	1
		.000	
N		123	123

**Correlation is significant at the 0.001 α (2 tail test)

From the above result. Compensation benefit has significant positive relationship with teacher morale (.000 <0.001). The results also have high correlation (.830**). Implying a strong agreement between compensation and benefit and teachers morale since probability value of .000 is less than the benchmark 0.001.

The null hypothesis is hereby rejected and alternate hypothesis accepted. This implies that compensation and benefits given to teachers can boost the morale of teacher in their workplace.

Table 3 Hypothesis Two Result

		Promotion	Teachers morale
Promotion	Pearson correlation	1	.870**
	Sig (2 tailed)		.000
	N	123	123
Teachers Morale	Person correlation (Sig. 2 tailed)	.870	1
		.000	
	N	123	123

**Correlation is significant at the 0.001 level (tailed)

Result of hypothesis two above revealed that promotion has significant positive relationship with teachers' morale. It can be deduced from the table that $P < 0.001$ meaning that the level of significance (.000) is less than 0.001. It is on this assumption that the null hypothesis rejected and alternate hypothesis accepted. This implies that when teachers are promoted as at when due their morale would go high.

Results of analysed hypothesis revealed that High performance work practice has significant positive relationship with teachers morale in public senior secondary school in Rivers State specifically it was found that compensation and benefit has significant and positive relationship with teacher's morale. Promotion has significant positive relationship with teachers' morale. These finding were in line with prior studies such as (Burhanudin & Hanuf, 2019; Ezeala & Oluwo, 2019; Anthony et al., 2021; Josephine et al., 2017; Grobler, 2018). The study carried out by (Burhanudin & Hanu, 2018) showed that employee benefit program measured in terms of social and facilitative benefits has a positive significant impact on employee morale and on employee performance. On the other hand (Ezeala & Oluwo, 2019) found out that promotion predicted teaching staff morale at a greater significance. Also Anthony et al. (2012) conducted an empirical work on high

performance work practices and turnover intention investigating the mediating role of employee morale and found out that HPWP measured in terms of training and reward also had significant positive effects on job satisfaction and morale initiating their rate of turnover intention. Josephine et al. (2017) carried out a study showing effect of compensation on Basic school teacher in the Northern zone of Ghana and found out that incentives and benefits significantly correlated with teachers' job satisfaction. Lastly Grobler, (2018) result on high performance work practices (HPWP'S) in determining success of south African companies shows the insignificance of HPWP'S interns of job work characteristics strategies and application of reward schemes can lead to low productivity and low commitment levels in an organization which will affect organization success.

Limitations

This study attempt to see the effect of HPWP on employee morale is limited to two dimensions of HPWP'S variable only, which are compensation and benefits and promotion. Though it is a very strong point in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State that can influence teacher's morale. On the other hand, there are several kinds of dimensions of HPWP that can also influence teacher's morale such as intensity of

training programme, career opportunities and organization culture or leadership type. So if the same research will be conducted with different object, procedure and variable it can be a different conclusion and result. In this study Sample is 123 teachers of a total of 608 teachers in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. The sample method does not reflect the perfect picture of the results of the analysis and the conclusions. Actually it is possible to conduct research to all the 608 teachers in Port Harcourt as the objects so that the result will be perfect to describe the actual condition in public senior secondary school in Rivers State. So that the result can help River State senior secondary school board to keep and develop the suitable compensation and benefit program.

Conclusion

In line with the finding this study concluded that High performance work practice measured in terms of compensation and benefits and promotion enhances the teacher's morale of public senior secondary school. Thus compensation and benefit has been found to increase teacher's morale by increasing their commitment, involvement and seriousness with their job. Also job satisfaction, high morale and high performance will be achieved when there is prompt payment of salaries and timely promotion as at when due. Thus the implication of this study is that Rivers state

Senior Secondary school board should ensure that teacher's compensation and benefit programmes are being implemented appropriately. Their promotion exercise should be an effective one not just a mere activity. When these practices are appropriately put to work it will boost the morale of the teachers and their performance and will lead to a greater achievement in the educational sector.

Contribution to Knowledge

The contributions of the study to the body knowledge on the relationship between HPWP'S and teacher's morale in public senior secondary school in Rivers State is stated as follows:

1. The study identifies compensation & benefits and promotion as strategic factors that boost teacher morale.
2. The study made recommendation to RSSSB (Rivers State Senior secondary school Board) on contemporary approaches toward enhancing teacher's morale and programmes in the educational sector.
3. The study provides empirical evidences on the influence of compensation and benefits and promotion on teacher's morale.
4. The study operational zed equity theory and social exchange theory into workable model that represents the interaction between HPWP'S and teacher's morale.

5. The inclusion of the dimension of HPWP'S (compensation and benefit and promotion) and the variable of teacher's morale into a single model. With the interaction between the variables distinguishes this study from similar studies in the past.

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